

PHONOSTYLISTICS. THE CONCEPT OF PHONOSTYLISTICS

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ANNOTATION

This article presents that modern style is considered a linguistic style when it is based on the linguistic foundation concepts of systematic and descriptive and is limited to the study of literary texts. But linguistic stylistics is the study of style based on linguistic principles. As a branch of applied linguistics, linguistic stylistics studies the styles of language. The analysis of linguistic style limits its investigation within the context of applied linguistics to the study language style.

And this is further guided by two interrelated factors called language level and language function. At the linguistic level, the study of style is carried out on different types of linguistic features. This article highlights the novel's distinctive stylistic features at the phonological level.

Keywords: phono stylistics, phonological level, branch of phonetics, phonetic phenomena, sociological content.

The Problems of Phono stylistics. Phono stylistics as a branch of phonetics.

Pronunciation is by no means homogeneous. It varies under the influence of numerous factors. These factors lie quite outside any possibility of signaling linguistic meaning so it is appropriate to refer to these factors as extralinguistic. The information about stylistic variations in learning, understanding and producing language is directly useful for the design, execution and evaluation of teaching phonetics. The branch of phonetics most usually applied for such information is phono stylistics. Phono stylistics is a rapidly developing and controversial field of study though a great deal of research work has been done in it. It would not be accurate to say that phono stylistics is a new branch of phonetics. It is rather a new way of looking at phonetic phenomena. Linguists were until recently not aware of this way of analysis and awareness came only as a result of detailed analysis of spoken speech.

Phono stylistics

Phonology Study of features of style at the phonological level, considered the basic level of linguistic analysis. Phonological processes are considered here as stylistic features. They are used to emphasize the author's point of emphasis on a particular word

or sound to reveal its importance in speech. They are used to highlight a character's mood and emotional intensity. Phonological features are also used to describe sociological context. Analysis of Golding's *Lord of the Flies* text highlights a number of phonological features such as phonemic reduction and altered physical form of words, etc. These phonological elements are treated carefully using examples from the novel.

Phonological reduction

Golding uses a number of phonological reductions in the discussions of the novel. Specifically, phonologically reduced utterances are made through the character 'Piggy'. In general, the utterances of all the characters have the linguistic feature of phonological reduction.

"They'd tell him at the airport".

"They're all dead" said Piggy "this is an island".

" Got' em just now".

"You're chief. You tell'em off".

"I'll bring'em back".

" I'm goin' to say".

"Is it safe? Ain't there a cliff?".

There are number of unusual phonological reductions found while analyzing the text of *Lord of the Flies*. Very often they are in line with the use of English in modern technological devices. They also indicate a kind of English use among the peer groups. In this novel such usages are used by the prominent characters. For example:

"What's yer name?"

"They're twins, Sam 'n Eric".

"Jus ' blurs, that's all. Hardly see my hand--".

"--then you come up here an' pinch my specs--".

"What 'ud happen to me?".

" What's grown-ups goin' to think?"

Phonological Stress and Intonation

The role of stress and intonation plays a vital role in determining the meaning either etically or emically. J.R. Firth (1969:193) has reported of evidence of some correlation of sounds with shapes. He states that "the general feature of voice quality is part of the phonetic mode of meaning of an English boy, a Frenchman, or a lady from New York. Stress is given to certain words or phrases by writers in order to give a special emphasis to that word or phrase in a particular context. The selection of linguistic units with a certain phonological pattern has a special significance always.

"Features of stress and intonation are stylized to reinforce the expressiveness of the message of the text in phonic medium in different kinds of situations, such as recitation of poems, delivery of sermons, lawyer's speech in the courtroom, an advertisement on radio or television, etc"(Suresh Kumar,1988:35). As a novelist, Golding has utilized this phenomenon in *Lord of the Flies*. He has used this phonological pattern to give certain emphasis and importance to the word or sound in that particular context.

SUMMARY COMPLETION: In this article, I can say that phonology studies the way in which phonetic means are used in one or another specific situation in order to create a regulating influence of a set of elements considered a foreign language.

The aim of phonology is to analyze all possible types of utterances with the main aim of identifying phonetic features, both segmental and suprasegmental, that are limited to certain types of contexts, to explain why these characteristics are used and classify them into categories according to their functions.

REFERENCES

1. Parmonova, N. (2022). Nasiba THE PHENOMENON OF CONVERSION
2. IN ENGLISH: THE PHENOMENON OF CONVERSION IN ENGLISH.
3. Teshaboyeva, N., & Mamayoqubova, S. (2020), COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH TO LANGUAGE TEACHING. In MOLODOY ISLEDOVATEL: VYZOVY I PERSPEKTIVY (rr. 409-414).
4. Teshaboyeva, N. (2020). LINGUISTIC PERSONALITY, ITS STRUCTURAL CHARACTERISTICS IN THE NEW PERSPECTIVE DIRECTIONS. In MOLODOY ISLEDOVATEL: VYZOVY PERSPEKTIVY (rr. 415-420).
5. Teshaboyeva, N. Z. (2019). TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH LITERATURE INTESSL AND TEFL CLASSROOMS. In SOVREMENNYE TECHNOLOGII: AKTUALNYE VOPROSY, DOSTIJENIYA I INNOVATsII (pp. 82-84).
6. Khidirova, D., & Teshaboeva, N. (2022). Pedagogical conditions for the development of healthy thinking in students. Current problems and development trends of modern innovation research: solutions and perspectives, 1(1), 120-122